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Analysis of Kemijeu Kelor (*Moringa Oleifera*) Herbal Teabag, Mint (Peppermint) and Bungong Jeumpa (*Michelia Champaca*)

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Abstract

Kemijeu herbal tea is made from Moringa leaves, mint leaves, and Bungong Jeumpa. Kemijeu herbal tea is rich in benefits, one of which is to increase body immunity and reduce cholesterol, so Kemijeu tea can be said to be an innovation from herbal tea in general. The purpose is to determine the analysis of Kemijeu herbal teabags of Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*), Mint (Peppermint), and Bungong Jeumpa (*Michelia champaca*). I made Kemijeu herbal tea using an experimental approach. According to Sugiyono (2018), the experimental method is a research method used to study the effect of one thing on another in controlled conditions systematically, logically, thoroughly, and by controlling the realism of the results obtained. The conclusion of this Kemijeu herbal tea research is that this tea is much loved because it has a delicious aroma and taste and unique color and texture. This tea also meets the requirements of the SNI 3836:2013 dry tea category because it matches the character of tea in general.

Keyword: Tea; Kemijeu; Herbal; Bungong Jeumpa

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INTRODUCTION

Kemijeu herbal tea is a combination of words from several types of plants consisting of Moringa leaves, mint leaves, and Bungong Jeumpa, also known as fragrant cempaka flowers. Nowadays, we really need to maintain health and consume a lot of herbal medicines to maintain endurance, such as the following herbal teas: Kemijeu herbal teabags or a mixture of Moringa leaves, mint leaves, and Bungong Jeumpa typical of Aceh.

But it can be used as a plant. In Acehnese culture, flowers are not just plants that are used as ornamental plants or perfume ingredients. which is efficacious for the health of the body. Every human being is inseparable from the name of disease; therefore, it is not uncommon for us to see many Acehnese people in our ancient times planting plants that can provide beauty, fragrance, beautiful eyes, and can also provide benefits to maintain body health. In the past, Acehnese people were very fond of planting plants that were beneficial for the health of the body and could be used as first aid drugs, for example, plants such as Moringa, Mint and. Bungong Jeumpa which could provide many benefits for the health of the body.

In making Kemijeu tea, there is one ingredient that comes from the Aceh region, which is the end of Indonesia. In addition, it is not uncommon to hear a folk song originating from Aceh Province entitled Bungong Jeumpa, which is one of the ingredients for making Kemijeu tea. The song itself can be said to be the result of inspiration from one of the forms of flora wealth in Aceh Province, namely Bungong Jeumpa Kuneng, also known as Yellow Cempaka Flower (*Michelia champaca*). Bungong Jeumpa has special characteristics, namely that the height of the tree can reach 50 m and the diameter of the trunk is 180 cm. This tree has a straight trunk and smooth gray-brown bark. The flowers are white or yellow and have a distinctive fragrance. The fruit is brown and small. Besides that, Bungong Jeumpa also has health benefits, namely: overcome flatulence, eliminate body odor, overcome inflammation of the respiratory tract, and overcome vaginal discharge.

Kemijeu herbal teabag has a main ingredient besides Bungong Jeumpa, namely Moringa leaves in Latin (*Moringa oleifera*). Moringa leaf plants are plants that are ovoid in shape, small, consisting of one stem, 1 to 3 cm long, 4 mm to 1 cm wide, with blunt leaf tips, rounded leaf bases, and flat leaf edges. Moringa leaves are often used as medicine and vegetables. Moringa leaves also have good benefits for the health of the body, namely: lower blood sugar levels, lower cholesterol, prevent cancer cells, and maintain eye health (Aziz, 2023; Zikrullah, 2023; Rudi, 2021; Shadigin, 2021; Ridha, 2020).

Besides Moringa leaves and Bungong Jeumpa, Kemijeu tea is also made from mint leaves, or Latin (peppermint). This mint leaf plant can also be used for its medicinal properties and is often used as the main ingredient in hot drinks such as tea. Mint leaves are usually ovoid and finely serrated. The color of the leaves is yellowish green; even this plant has certain characteristics that can be distinguished by color variations, such as yellow dots and green leaves, and has a red body. In addition, mint leaves are also characterized by a spicy flavor and a refreshing aroma. Behind the cool and refreshing sensation. Mint leaves also have many different benefits for the body, specifically: overcoming indigestion, relieving irritable bowel syndrome, improving brain function, and losing weight (Cristina, 2024; Munidar, 2024; Rahmadani, 2024; Johan, 2024).

Kemijeu herbal tea using Bungong Jeumpa, Moringa leaves, and Mint leaves is one of the teas that innovates and benefits the health of the body. In addition to innovating and benefiting

health, this herbal tea also makes it easier for people if they want to make herbal tea because Kemijeu herbal tea is made from plants that we can easily find in the surrounding environment.

METHOD

Time and Place of Research

The research was carried out at the Science Lab of MTsN 1 Model Banda Aceh, and the research schedule was carried out from August to September.

Data Sources, Tools and Materials

The data sources in this study were untrained panelists, totaling eight (eight) people. The panelists are research teachers and some students of MTsN 1 Model Banda Aceh.

Tools and Materials

a. Tools

- Scissors
- Analytical scales
- Drying cabinet
- Drying container
- Container for brewing
- Tea bags
- Slicing blender or suitcase

b. Materials

- Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*)
- Mint (Peppermint)
- Bungong Jeumpa Kuneng (*Michelia champaca* L.) Herbal Tea Making

Making Kemijeu herbal tea, namely Moringa leaves, mint leaves, and Bungong Jeumpa that have been picked, weighed first with analytical scales, then washed under running water and drained, then cut into smaller parts, then placed in a container in the sun until it dries completely. The next stage is the destruction of dried Bungong Jeumpa Kuneng, mint leaves, and moringa leaves with a slicing blender or suitcase. Furthermore, it is weighed according to the composition, then put into tea bags, and the last stage of herbal teabags can be brewed first.

Data Acquisition

The method used in this research is the experimental method with organoleptic assessment. According to Sugiyono (2018), the experimental method is a research method used to find the effect of one thing on another in controlled conditions systematically, logically, thoroughly, and in accordance with the reality of the results obtained. Stages in experimental research include collection activities, preparation and manufacture of herbal tea, and testing of tea products based on a table of dry tea requirements according to standard 7 SNI 3836:2013, namely the test of the state of steeping water (color, smell, taste, texture) with typical requirements for tea products.

The organoleptic assessment is used to assess the quality of herbal tea products. According to Triastini (2018), organoleptic is also called sensory assessment. In organoleptic assessment or sensory assessment, there are criteria that are tested, namely: Testing of tea

products based on the table of dry tea requirements according to SNI 3836:2013, namely the test of the state of steeping water (color, smell, taste) with the typical requirements of tea products. The data collection technique with organoleptic assessment is presented in Appendix 1.

Furthermore, after filling out the organoleptic test questionnaire, each panelist was given one herbal tea bag to try. Next, the panelists filled out a questionnaire on the efficacy of Kemijeu herbal tea with a Likrt scale. Which consists of positive statements: SS = 3, S = 2, TS = 1, and negative statements: SS = 1, S = 2, TS = 3. Furthermore, the researchers conducted open interviews about the panelists' responses to the existence of Kemijeu herbal teabags of Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*), Mint (Peppermint), and Bungong Jeumpa (*Michelia champaca*).

Data Processing and Analysis

Data collection tools in the following research are:

- Organoleptic test questionnaire
- Open-ended interview guideline

The data processing method is carried out by giving brewed Kemijeu tea to the panelists. After the tea has been tried, the researcher starts giving the questionnaire to the panelists to fill in the appropriate statements according to the panelists regarding herbal tea, as in the attachment. After giving the questionnaire and having been filled in by the panelists, the researcher starts processing the data as in the research results.

Data analysis in this study using the percentage formula with the equation:

$$P = X \times 100\%$$

(Sudijono, 2018)

Description:

P = Percentage number

f = Frequency of Kemijeu herbal tea efficacy questionnaire scores N = Number of panelists

Therefore, the analysis carried out in this study is a percentage calculation with an organoleptic test with a hedonic scale on Kemijeu tea brewing with taste, aroma, and color and texture parameters.

FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Finding

This tea is made from main ingredients that have many benefits for the health of the body. Such as moringa leaves and mint leaves, which can contribute vitamin C to our body, and Bungong Jeumpa, which overcomes diseases of the respiratory tract. In this study, there are several elements that are tested, namely, aroma, taste, color, and texture. This study requires a total of 8 panelists. Here are the results:

Table 1. Aroma Percentage of Kemijeu Tea

AROMA			
Answer	Number of Answers	Answer Score	Percentage

SS	7	21	87.5
S	1	2	12.5
TS	0	0	0

Based on Table 1 above, it can be explained that the aroma of Kemijeu tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 87.5%, S = 12.5%, and TS = 0%.

Table 2: Percentage of Kemijeu Tea Flavor

TASTE			
Answer	Number of Answers	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	3	9	37,5
S	5	10	62.5
TS	0	0	0

Based on Table 2 above, it can be explained that the taste of Kemijeu tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 37.5%, S = 62.5%, and TS = 0%.

Table 3. Percentage of Kemijeu Tea Color

COLOR			
Answer	Number of Answers	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	3	9	37,5
S	5	10	62.5
TS	0	0	0

Based on Table 3 above, it can be explained that the color of Kemijeu tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 37.5%, S = 62.5%, and TS = 0%.

Table 4. Percentage of Kemijeu Tea Texture

TEXTURE			
Answer	Number of Answers	Answer Score	Percentage
SS	7	21	87.5
S	1	2	12.5
TS	0	0	0

Based on Table 4.4 above, it can be explained that the texture of Kemijeu herbal tea is much liked and has a percentage of SS = 87.5%, S = 12.5%, and TS = 0%.

Discussion

From the results of the research that has been done, there are many positive statements about the results of the Kemijeu herbal tea research. Besides having a distinctive aroma, color, and taste, Kemijeu herbal tea is rich in health benefits. The results of the analysis of Kemijeu herbal tea show that the aroma of Kemijeu tea has a percentage of SS = 87.5%, S = 12.5%, and TS = 0%. The taste of Kemijeu tea has a percentage of SS = 37.5%, S = 62.5%, and TS = 0%. The color of Kemijeu tea has a percentage of SS = 37.5%, S = 62.5%, and TS = 0%. The texture of Kemijeu herbal tea has a percentage of SS = 87.5% and S = 12.5%. Panelists stated that Kemijeu tea products, based on the test of steeping water conditions (color, smell, taste), were in accordance with the typical requirements of tea products and the requirements for dry tea according to standard 7 SNI 3836:2013. It can be concluded that Kemijeu tea products meet SNI standards. According to Arinda Nur Ariva (2020) SNI 3836:2013, the aroma of dry tea that meets the standard is the aroma of typical tea with no foreign odor. The color of dried tea that meets the standard is a typical tea-like color, which is reddish brown or golden yellow. The panelists' assessment of the taste of cascara tea was carried out by observing the taste using the sense of taste (tongue), then assessing the panelists' preference in the form of a preference scale that was felt when tasting the tea.

Furthermore, this is in line with research (Saragih, 2014), which says that the aroma of t2w2 treatment is favored by panelists. This is because the t2w2 treatment is dried at 50 oC with a drying time of 3 hours so that the aromatic compounds have evaporated, which causes the results of steeping Torbangun leaf tea to be much liked by panelists. Furthermore, it is also in line with the results of research (Dewitayani, 2019), which says that the concentration of ginger in ruku-ruku tea bags has a significant effect ($P > 0.01$) on the taste of ruku-ruku tea. This happens because the taste of ginger is more dominant than the taste of ruku-ruku, so when brewed, it can cover the taste of ruku-ruku tea. This is in line with the results of research (Saragih, 2014), which says that the interaction of temperature and drying time has a very significant effect on the level of liking of the color of Torbangun leaf tea, so it is necessary to conduct a DMRT further test to determine the effect of the interaction of temperature and drying time on the color of Torbangun leaf tea. This is in line with research (Jovita Kurnia Dewi, 2014), which says the SNI standard for green tea bags is a maximum of 16.50%, so it can be said that the tea bag product slightly meets the standard.

CONCLUSION

Kemijeu tea is tea derived from Moringa leaves, Mint leaves, and Bungong Jeumpa. Kemijeu herbal tea is one of the teas that is a variation of herbal tea in general because it is made from mixed plants, namely Moringa leaves, Mint leaves, and Bungong Jeumpa, which are now difficult to get. Besides that, tea is also rich in benefits and can increase the immunity of the human body. As well as being one of the alternative medicines made from natural ingredients without being made from chemicals, this tea has the uniqueness of being made from Bungong Jeumpa, which is now difficult to get. And based on the results and discussion, it can be concluded that the conclusion of this Kemijeu herbal tea research is that this tea is much liked because it has a delicious aroma and taste and a unique color and texture. According to SNI 3836:2013, the aroma of dried tea that meets the standard is the aroma of typical tea with no foreign odor. The color of dried tea that meets the standard is a typical tea-like color, which is reddish brown or golden yellow. Panelists' assessment of the taste of tea is done by observing the taste using the sense of

taste (tongue), then assessing the panelists' preference in the form of a scale of preference felt when tasting the tea.

Suggestion

Although researchers want perfection in the process of making this Kemijeu tea, in reality there are still many shortcomings in making this tea due to the lack of Bungong Jeumpa capacity, which is a little difficult because it has a season to be easily obtained.

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